

Conventional to point of care devices for the detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

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Abstract: Tuberculosis (TB) is a deadly illness that mostly affects the lungs and is caused by the pathogenic bacterium *M. tuberculosis*. Tuberculosis bacteria transmit from individual to individual via tiny respiratory droplets. The illness usually affects the lungs (pulmonary tuberculosis), but it could also impact other parts of the body (extra-pulmonary TB). *M. tuberculosis* infects around a 1/4th of the world's population. The contamination of TB is a serious public health concern because it may develop as a complication of acquired immune deficiency syndrome infection (AIDS). As a result, detecting, identifying, and quantifying *M. tuberculosis* is critical for worldwide public health protection. In clinical diagnosis, food analysis, bioprocess, and environmental monitoring, biosensing technologies have the potential to enhance TB detection and supervision. For the detection of *M. tuberculosis*, a range of transferrable, fast, and sensitive biosensors with instant "on-the-spot" interpretation has been developed. TB is a disease that is caused by interplay of genetic components, activity recognition, and fundamental signaling transduction processes. The present review mainly concerns the current developments in electrochemical biosensors for the analysis of pathogenic bacteria, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Besides this, the advantages of biosensors over conventional methods have also been discussed.

Keywords: Tuberculosis; Biosensors; Diagnostics; Conventional methods.

1. Introduction

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is one of the most threatening pathogenic bacteria that cause tuberculosis (TB) - a common infectious disease that usually affects lungs as well as other body parts and still remains the second leading cause of death (1). *M. tuberculosis* can remain inactive or in a sleeping state for many years without showing any symptoms or spreading to other parts of the body, but as soon as the immune system of the host becomes deteriorates, the bacteria turn into active form and infects mainly lungs along with other body parts (2). Tuberculosis can be of two types-pulmonary TB (PTB), which affects the lungs, and extra pulmonary TB (EPTB), which involves organs other than the lungs such as skin, bones, joints, lymph nodes, pleura, etc. It is more prevalent than PTB (3). TB may afflict anybody, anywhere, although the majority of individuals who contract the disease are adults; males are more likely to contract the disease than women, and 30 high-TB-burden nations account for over 90% of those who contract the disease each year. People infected by TB typically experience economic difficulties, vulnerability, marginalization, stigma, and prejudice since TB is a disease of poverty. Tuberculosis is both curable and preventive. About 85% of persons who get tuberculosis may be effectively treated with a 6-month medication regimen, which also has the added benefit of preventing illness from spreading (4). Diagnosis of EPTB involves a wide range of suspicion as symptoms and signs can be unclear and sometimes occurs in normal chest x-rays; also, delayed detection of EPTB increases the rate of mortality and morbidity (5). Despite the worldwide elimination efforts for this disease, TB is still a global public health concern, mainly in low- and middle-income countries (6).

Smear microscopy, chest radiography, tuberculin skin testing, as well as culture procedures are widely employed in the detection of *M. tuberculosis*;

however, microscopy is laborious & time-consuming method. Culturing takes about 6-8 weeks; they are very complicated and have only about 85% sensitivity. Chest radiography and tuberculin skin tests are not commonly used since they are ineffective because tuberculosis (TB) mimics pneumonia symptoms, and a standard radiological x-ray cannot discriminate between the two. This reduces the use of these techniques since they are slow in detecting tuberculosis. (7,8). Molecular methods include non-amplification and amplification-based procedures like polymerase chain reaction (PCR), target amplification, loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), etc. These approaches are acknowledged to be sensitive but then again, at the same time, they are very much time intense and need a long assay time (9). Therefore, the development of a portable or transferable, real-time, sensitive, quick, and precise technique for *M. tuberculosis* detection is essential for the inhibition of tuberculosis. Biosensing technologies are ideally suited for this goal, as sensing technology research has grown significantly in recent years (10). Biosensors may be defined as bio-analytical tools that translate biotic (any biological or living) responses into a measurable or computable signal such as an electrical signal. Biosensors act as a pointer of biological molecules with the essential structures and features of on-spot assay and multiple analyses systems (11). Biosensors are an irresistible tool that is able to provide immediate information on a disease outburst. Biosensors play an extraordinary role in the field of food analysis, water management, environmental monitoring, clinical analysis, agriculture, and many more. Biosensors offer the possibility of real-time monitoring, i.e., on-the-spot analysis that is the current needs worldwide (12).

Here, a brief review of various biosensing techniques that are either already in use or under progress for the detection of *M. tuberculosis* is presented. The courtesy of the review will be mainly on

the evolving biosensor approaches that are compared to conventional techniques.

2. Epidemiology

Human being has fought against tuberculosis, for about 4000 years. Early in the seventh century BC, TB-like symptoms were documented in Assyria. Its mortality rate is advanced than that of HIV/AIDS. According to the World tuberculosis report by WHO 2020, globally, an estimated 10.0 million (range, 8.9–11.0 million) people fell ill with TB in 2019. There were an estimated 1.2 million (range, 1.1– 1.3 million) TB deaths among HIV-negative people in 2019 (a reduction from 1.7 million in 2000), and an additional 208 000 deaths (range, 177 000–242 000) among HIV-positive people (a reduction from 678 000 in 2000). Men (aged ≥ 15 years) accounted for 56% of the people who developed TB in 2019; women accounted for 32%, and children (aged more than 15 years) for 12 %. Among all those people, 8.5% are those living with HIV. Geographically, most people who developed TB in 2019 were in the WHO regions of South-East Asia (44%), Africa (25%), and the Western Pacific (18%), with smaller percentages in the Eastern Mediterranean (8.2%), the Americas (2.9%) and Europe (2.5%). Eight countries accounted for two-thirds of the global total: India (26%), Indonesia (8.5%), China (8.4%), the Philippines (6.0%), Pakistan (5.7%), Nigeria (4.4%), Bangladesh (3.6%) and South Africa (3.6%). The other 22 other countries in WHO's list of 30 high TB burden countries accounted for 21% of the global total (13). According to the research, early diagnosis and conventional treatment can prevent the majority of TB-related fatalities. Between 2000 and 2016, early diagnosis and proper treatment saved the lives of nearly 53 million tuberculosis patients. Despite the fact that many individuals with tuberculosis can be correctly diagnosed and treated, there are still gaps in the diagnosis and treatment of the disease. Poverty, HIV/AIDS, malnutrition, and tobacco all play a bigger

role in TB prevention and control in most countries with a high TB burden (14).

3. Conventional TB diagnostics

Symptoms of TB appear very deliberately. Many times, it is extremely problematic to diagnose whether in its active form or inactive form, but when a person develops any lung disease and constitutional symptoms lasting for more than two weeks, it is mandatory to check whether a person has TB. TB can be prohibited by early detection and on-time proper treatment. Initial diagnosis of tuberculosis requires regular medical check-ups of a person who is at high risk of TB (15). There are various methods available for TB diagnosis. Figure 1 shows methods and their classifications for the diagnosis of TB.

3.1 Immunological and microbiological tests

Immunological and microbiological methods include smear microscopy (16), tuberculin skin test (17), radiometric detection test (18), immunology-based assays (19), culturing and plating methods (20), and many more. In spite of drawbacks, for example, more time requirement and being expensive often used with the blend of other methods to yield much more vigorous outcomes.

3.1.1 Smear Microscopy

The smear Microscopy test is among the oldest and common methods used for the diagnosis of TB. Stained sputum or similar clinical material is examined under a microscope. Commonly Zeihl Neelsen stain is used for staining. Smear microscopy results largely depend upon the type of stain used, type of clinical specimen, amount of specimen, and the experience that a person holds who is examining the specimen (16).

It is worth mentioning some of the disadvantages of this technique. It doesn't show much accuracy. It requires highly equipped labs, requires multiple stages in the procedures, good quality reagents,

highly experienced examiners that make it unfit for quick finding of TB. Because serial sputum exams are required, some patients who do not return for further sputum examinations are referred to as "diagnostic defaulters." It also has a poor track record in extra-pulmonary tuberculosis, pediatric tuberculosis, and patients co-infected with HIV and tuberculosis (21-23).

3.1.2 Tuberculin skin test

It is also known as Mantoux tuberculin skin test (TST). It is performed by injecting a minor volume of tuberculin fluid (known as TB antigen) into the skin on the lower area of the arm. The result is obtained with 3-4 days.

The method is sensitive, but positive results don't give conclusive evidence of whether TB is in its active form or not. Takes a lot of time in obtaining result and patients have to make multiple visits to the expertise that makes it a big complex (24, 25).

3.1.3 Radiometric detection test

This refers to simple chest radiography or chest x-ray. Chest x-rays use a minor dosage of ionizing radioactivity to produce pictures of the inner of the chest. They are employed to identify and analyze the conditions affecting the chest area. Post-anterior radiography of the patient's chest area is an obligatory portion of each estimation for TB. The main disadvantage is the poor sensitivity as only a chest x-ray cannot confirm a person has TB infection (26).

3.1.4 Culture

The culturing and plating method is one of the oldest bacterial detection techniques and remains the standard detection method. Culture detection tests involve a long procedure of sample collection, serial dilution, media preparation, plating on suitable media then waiting for the visible colonies. The incubation time is about 72 hours for growing *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* as its growth rate is very slow (27). Cultures can only

distinguish as rare as 10 mycobacteria/mL of the given sample; however, at minimum 5000 mycobacteria/mL are vital for a positive smear. Usually, solid media was used for culturing *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and it takes about 6 weeks to visualize the colonies, but now liquid media has taken place and reduced the time to 2 weeks. Once the growth is visualized, mycobacteria can be easily identified and analyzed. For detecting active Tb, mycobacterial culture remains the orientation average with a specificity of about 98 % and 80-85% of sensitivity (28).

Although this technique is extremely subtle nonetheless, at the same time, it takes more than 2 weeks to show accurate results. It even requires a proper lab for culture, which makes it an incompetent method for detecting TB (29).

3.1.5 Immunological based assays

Immunological-based assays (30) for the detection of immune complexes, antibodies, antigens have struggled for many years. They are based on the specific binding of antibodies and antigens. These assays mainly diagnose humoral immune response against T-cell-based assays that detect cellular immunity. A large variety of kits are available commercially that are focused upon antibody detection, such as ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay), Immunomagnetic separation (IMS), Immunofluorescence, Immunoelectrophoretic assay, ELFA (Enzyme-linked fluorescent assay), LAM-ELISA (Lipoarabinomannan ELISA), Enzyme-linked immunospot- ELISPOT (31). These assays totally depend upon antibody recognition of antigen and other bio-molecules that are specific to the target (32). The only disadvantage is low sensitivity and specificity as it only detects the past antibodies (33).

Dheda et al. examined the clinical usefulness of a commercial lipoarabinomannan (LAM-ELISA) test for TB detection in HIV-infected patients utilizing urine and

Table 1: Current methods used to detect TB, procedure, time taken in obtaining result and accuracy.

Method	Procedure	Accuracy	Time required	References
Immunology based assays	Detection of humoral immune response as opposed to T- cell based assays.	Low sensitivity and specificity as it only detects the past antibodies produced.	Very fast results. Take only about 30 min.	(40)
Smear microscopy	Samples from coughed up or expectorated sputum is prepared and stained with Ziehl Neelsen stain and studied under the microscope.	Sensitivity of only about 50-60%.	Fast results within 30 min.	(41)
Tuberculin skin testing	Inject measured amount of TB antigen in the top layer of skin and read the indurations within 2-3 days.	Highly sensitive but at the same time it cannot confirm whether TB is in its active form or not. Therefore, its use in detecting Tb is quite limited.	48- 72 hours.	(17)
Radiometric detection test	Preparation of x-ray films.	Poor sensitivity as only chest x-ray cannot approve that a person has TB.	Takes about 20-30 min for the procedure and time needed for interpreting is 48-72 hours.	(42)
<i>M.tuberculosis</i> culture	Inoculation of clinical samples on the growth media like Luria Bertani media and inoculating at 37°C for 4-8 weeks.	It gives accurate results but due to its time-consuming nature and various lab facilities requirement its use is limited.	Takes about 4-8 weeks.	(43)

Molecular methods	This allows sequences of DNA to be amplified in vitro even when only a few copies of mycobacteria are present, so that amount of amplified DNA can be rapidly visualized and identified.	Highly sensitive but are very costly as they require laboratory settings.	Gives results in about 6-7 hours.	(44)
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Figure 1: Conventional methods for the detection of TB

sputum samples. LAM was assessed in sputum and urine samples collected from 500 ambulant individuals with probable tuberculosis. Due to test cross-reactivity with numerous mouth-residing organisms, including actinomycetes and Nocardia species, Sputum-LAM had excellent sensitivity of around 86 percent but low

specificity of 15 percent (34). Commercially available LAM detection tests have limited sensitivity and are largely reliant on the patient's immunological state, with advanced HIV infection performing well. Amin et al., 2018, used two innovative LAM-based methods to make a sensitive detection of tuberculosis infection: Using

murine and human monoclonal antibodies, capture ELISA was used to identify LAM in matched urine and serum samples, as well as detection of (-)-d-arabinofuranose and tuberculostearic acid (TBSA). Based on GC/MS detection of the two LAM-surrogates, d-arabinose and tuberculostearic acid (TBSA), LAM in patient urine was identified in a concentration range of 3–28 ng/mL, accurately diagnosing TB status with a sensitivity of 99 percent and specificity of around 84 percent. The ELISA test exhibited a high sensitivity of 98% and specificity of 92%, respectively (35).

3.2 Molecular methods

Molecular methods constitute a wide variety of detection assays that depend upon nucleic acid amplification to enhance the diagnosis of pathogens. Nucleic acid amplification tests (NATs) have contributed to the growth of tests with high positive prediction rates (98-99 percent) and reduced negative prediction results in recent years. Direct amplification tests, also known as NATs, amplify nucleic acid reagents specific to the *M. tuberculosis* complex. The advantage of the amplification approach over other methods is its sensitivity, which is the highest of all. These methods may be used on stored materials, and results can be received in as little as 6-8 hours (36). NATs are accessible as commercial kits. They are employed widely as in-house assays. In-house tests are laboratory-developed PCR assays. Commercial kits are quite expensive; therefore, many countries prefer to use PCR assays (37). PCR allows the sequence of DNA to be amplified in vitro even when only a few copies of mycobacterium are present. PCR shows a high sensitivity for pulmonary TB as in the recent study performed in Bangladesh, the sensitivity and specificity of PCR using IS6110 to be 94.74% and 100%, which shows that PCR technique is a rapid and sensitive method for pulmonary TB (38). But at the same time, it is not true with the case of extra-pulmonary TB. Sharma

et al., 2016 developed Real-time immuno-PCR (RT-I-PCR) for the detection of mycobacterial PstS1. The assay showed a wide dynamic range of 10 ng/mL to 1 pg/mL in body fluids of tuberculosis (TB) patients, which may monitor the dynamics of disease (39).

Since all the traditional methods for detecting pathogenic bacteria are time-consuming, there is a requirement for a new technology that is rapid, reliable, simple, specific, and sensitive. In addition, it should be able for in situ real-time monitoring at a low cost. In recent years there has been much research activity in the area of the biosensor.

4. Biosensors for Tuberculosis detection

Most of the methods mentioned above require highly skilled and expert staff well-equipped lab facilities. They are time-consuming and laborious, and apart from all, they are not 100% specific and sensitive. Therefore, there is a need for a rapid, real-time, specific, and portable system for detecting TB. Advancements in the field of biosensing technology have given new hope for scientists as it has proven to be a rapid method for diagnosing this dangerous disease (15).

4.1 Introduction to Biosensors

A biosensor is a systematic device that translates a biological response into a measurable electrical signal. It comprises two main components: a bioreceptor and a biorecognition element, which recognizes events into a measurable electronic signal. A bioreceptor can be any tissue, microorganism, organelle, enzyme, cell, antibody, etc. The transduction may be optical, electrochemical, thermometric, magnetic, and micromechanical or combinations of one or more of the above-mentioned techniques (Figure 2) (45). Biosensors produce a signal proportional to the specific interaction between the analyte and the recognition element present on the biosensor (46). The beginning of biosensors may be dated to 1962, when Clark, known as the father of the biosensor concept, published an experiment in which

glucose oxidase was entrapped at a Clark oxygen electrode using a dialysis membrane (47). Biosensors can detect a wide range of targets, from small protein molecules to large pathogens.

The advantages of biosensors over conventional diagnostic techniques are many. Some of them are as stated below:

1. Biosensors are technically pro as they allow single-step detection. They didn't require multiple attempts.
2. Biosensors are very much easy to use; they don't require professionals to use them. They are very much user-friendly.
3. Biosensors are very rapid as compared to other conventional diagnostic techniques. They give quick responses typically within few minutes and have good control over measurement (48).

Biosensors can be classified into two categories depending on their biorecognition element (bioreceptor) and the detection method, i.e., transducers. Figure.2 shows the classification of biosensors). The biorecognition elements, mainly in nucleic acid sensors, can be further divided into DNA, RNA, PNA, and Aptamer. On the basis of the transducing element, biosensors can be categorized as electrochemical, optical, piezoelectric, and thermal sensors. Among the various biosensors, electrochemical biosensors have gained considerable interest as bioanalytical devices and have played an important role in the detection of desired pathogens (49, 50). Biosensor on the basis of bioreceptor employed for detecting TB

4.2. DNA based sensors

DNA sensors have revolutionized modern analysis due to their stability and low cost, making them a versatile building block for the fabrication of new devices in nanotechnology and biosensor technology. Most literature has focused on genosensors due to their high specificity. Electrochemical DNA sensors are also effective tools for the rapid detection of pathogens with

high sensitivity and selectivity. The most crucial step in the preparation is the surface immobilization of the DNA strands. Subsequent interaction with a specific fragment gene from the pathogen causes changes in the DNA structure or the assembly and the electrochemical properties of the interface, which can be assessed using impedimetric as well as voltammetric readouts (51). Electrochemical detection of DNA is divided into direct and indirect approaches. The direct methods use the electric activity of DNA itself or the changes in the interfacial properties of the DNA-modified electrode, such as capacitance, conductivity, or impedance. The indirect methods rely on the use of electrochemical active DNA intercalators (e.g., methylene blue) or labels such as enzymes, redox mediators, and particles to amplify the readouts (52). The literature is rather rich, but some examples are highlighted in the following section (Table 2).

Miodek et al. reported an E- DNA sensor of *M. tuberculosis* based on the electrochemical assembly of nanomaterials. Two-step electrochemical patterning methods have been employed to elaborate composite nanomaterials formed with multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) coated with polypyrrole (PPy) and redox PAMAM dendrimers (53).

Torati et al. reported an electrochemical biosensor for *M. tuberculosis* DNA detection based on gold nanotubes array electrode platform. The AuNTsA was used as an electrode for the fabrication of DNA hybridization biosensor for detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* DNA. The developed electrochemical DNA biosensor shows a good linear range of complementary DNA concentration from 0.01 ng/ μ L to 100 ng/ μ L with a high detection limit (54).

Figure 2: Classification of Biosensor on the basis of bioreceptor element and transducing element

4.3. Antibody based sensors

The concept of using immunological components as sensing agents was first described within an immunoassay for plasma insulin in human subjects. Biosensors can incorporate many different biological sensing agents, e.g., enzymes, cell receptors, nucleic acids, microorganisms, and, in the case of antibody-based biosensors, antibodies or antibody fragments. Antibody-based biosensors or Immunosensors employ the high Ab/Ag specificity to detect the presence of its analyte. Immunosensors can be either direct or indirect, meaning that the detection mechanism operates directly via the Ab/Ag interaction, or a further label, such as an enzyme or fluorescent molecule, is used to detect whether a binding event has occurred (55). Antibody-

modified sensors allow the fast and sensitive analysis of *M. tuberculosis*. Antibody-based sensors provide an opportunity to gain new insight to create sensitive and simple immunoassay devices in the detection of *M. tuberculosis*. Electrochemical immunosensors combine the high specificity of traditional immunochemical methods with the low detection limits of the modern electrochemical system. For the design of an electrochemical immunosensor, the crucial steps are the choice of the basis electrode and the immobilization of the immune reagent onto the electrode surface. A wide variety of electrodes have been used as support to fabricate immunosensor devices, including carbon paste electrodes, glassy carbon electrodes, or gold electrodes, and many more.

Diouani et al. 2017 reported a miniature electrochemical biosensor for the detection of ESAT-6 (Early secreted antigenic target 6- kDa protein), the virulent factor of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Firstly, Anti-ESAT-6 antibodies were covalently immobilized on the surface of a gold screen-printed electrode functionalized through a self-assembled thiol monolayer. Interaction between the bio-receptor and ESAT-6 antigen was appraised by square wave voltammetry method using $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-4-}$ as a redox probe. The detection limit of ESAT-6 antigen was 7 ng/ml making it a sensitive sensor for detection (56).

Sepulveda et al. reported bioelectrochemical detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ESAT-6 in an antibody-based bio-microsystem. This development validates a non-invasive method to electrically monitor the assembly process of electro-immunosensors and a tool for its further measure for detection of relevant antigens (57).

Montoya et al. reported a high fundamental frequency (HFF)-based QCM Immunosensor for tuberculosis detection. Under optimized conditions, the HFF immunosensor calibration curve for 38 kDa determination showed a limit of detection as low as 11 ng mL⁻¹ of the biomarker. The high detectability attained by this immunosensor, in the picomolar range, makes it a promising tool for the easy, direct, and sensitive detection of the tuberculosis biomarker in biological fluids such as sputum (58).

4.4. Aptamer based sensors

Aptamers are nucleic acid-based (DNA or RNA) affinity probes that provide a number of advantages over Abs, including temperature stability, low cost, and reusability. Aptamers represent an alternative to antibodies as recognition elements in biosensors. The aptamer selection can be performed under real matrix conditions, which is particularly useful for environmental and food samples. Aptamers can be modified for immobilization

purposes and labeled with reporter molecules without affecting their affinity. As nucleic acid sequences, aptamers can be subjected to repeated cycles of denaturation and renaturation; this makes it possible to regenerate the immobilized biocomponent function for reuse. Another significant advantage of aptamers stems from the relative simplicity with which nucleic acid sequences can be engineered to integrate affinity and signal-transducing moieties into the same molecule. O'Sullivan first reviewed the introduction of aptamers as potential biorecognition molecules in biosensors in 2002. One of the main advantages of electrical aptasensors is that sensitivity can be enhanced by attaching biocatalytic labels to the aptamer-target complexes to amplify the detection signal. Furthermore, electrical aptasensors are more convenient for on-field detection applications since they do not require expensive optical instruments. Additionally, it is possible to use label-free and reusable detection systems. In most cases, protein electrical aptasensors can be easily reused after washing off the target protein. Immunological biosensors cannot do this because both target and sensing elements (antibodies) are proteins.

5. Biosensor on the basis of transducing element for detecting TB

5.1 Electrochemical Biosensors

These are sensors that employ electrochemical interrogation together with current, potential, and impedance changes to transduce the biological recognition event. They were first developed in 1962 with the glucose electrode and combine the analytical power of techniques such as voltammetry, potentiometry, and conductometry with the specificity of biological recognition. On comparing with nearly all other analytical techniques, electrochemical detection assays have the advantage of being inexpensive, robust, and quite simple to operate (59). An electrochemical

Table 2: Summary of various biosensors employed for detecting *M. Tuberculosis*

Methodology	Samples analyzed	Limit of detection (LOD)	year
Nucleic- acid sensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	0.065 ng/L	2010
Gold Nanoparticle- based electrochemical biosensor	<i>Mycobacterium</i> sp. Genomic DNA	1.25 ng/ml	2011
DNA-based Biosensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex	0.01 ng/l	2011
Impedimetric nucleic acid biosensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	-	2011
Aptamer based biosensor	Interferon (IFN)- γ	0.06 nM	2010
Piezoelectric biosensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	0.5 to 30 μ g/ml	2010
DNA based biosensor	Specific DNA insertion sequence IS6110 of <i>M. tuberculosis</i>	-	2014
DNA biosensor based on electrochemical assembly of nanomaterials	Sequence of Drug resistance <i>M. tuberculosis</i>	-	2015
Aptamer based electrochemical biosensor	Interferon-gamma (IFN- γ)	83 pM	2015
Immunosensor based on surface Plasmon resonance (SPR)	Antibody against <i>M. tuberculosis</i>	-	2012
Immunosensor based on Surface plasmon resonance (SPR)	Human Interferon-gamma (HIFN- γ) in diluted blood plasma samples	0.2 nM	2012
Label- free DNA based Biosensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> and Rifampicin resistance	2 pg/ml	2015
Nanogapped Impedimetric immunosensor	16 kDa heat shock protein (16 kDa HSP) against <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> (MT)	100 fM	2016
Electrochemical PNA biosensor based on functionalized graphene oxide	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> DNA sequence	8.948×10^{-13} M	2016
Lateral flow Nucleic acid biosensors	Mutations causing Multi- drug resistant TB (MDR-TB).	-	2016
Electrochemical immunosensor based on disposable ITO	Interferon- γ (IFN- γ).	0.048 pg/mL	2016
Aptamer based voltammetric biosensor	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> antigen MPT64	$0.9 \text{ fg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$	2017
SPR biosensor integrated with a nested PCR technique	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex	63 pg/mL	2018

Electrochemical aptasensorbased on novel signal generation and amplification	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> MPT64 antigen in human serum	20 fG/mL	2017
Electrochemical Aptasensor using Optimized Surface Chemistry	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> Secreted Protein MPT64 in Human Serum	81pM	2019
Liquid crystal based aptasensor	Interferon- γ (IFN- γ) in human blood	1 pM (17 pg/ml)	2018

biosensor is a self-contained integrated device capable of providing specific quantitative or semi-quantitative analytical information using a biological recognition element (biochemical receptor) engaged in direct spatial contact with an electrochemical transduction element (e.g., a pair of electrodes or field-effect transistors).

Electrochemical biosensors are among the most widely utilized biosensors now for detecting not only tuberculosis but a wide range of other illnesses. The ability to miniaturize and multiplex electrochemical sensing devices and build flexible, disposable, and low-cost electrochemical sensing devices has made electrochemical sensors very appealing for many applications where sensitivity, ease of operation, quick response time, and low cost are required. The advancements in electrochemical biosensor detection limits and specificity reported over the last decade are largely due to advances in materials science and the subsequent availability of a wide range of nanomaterials and composite materials with good electrical conductivity and/or catalytic activity. Because most electrochemical sensors are label-free sensing devices, they offer a lot of promise for pathogen detection and have been widely regarded as a cheaper and more powerful alternative to molecular pathogen detection (60).

5.2 Colorimetric sensors

An approach for the ultrasensitive and affordable naked-eye detection and diagnosis of tuberculosis (TB) was studied by Mohd Bakhori et al., 2018 utilizing

plasmonic enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) via antibody-antigen interaction. The biocatalytic cycle and intracellular enzymes effectively produced gold nanoparticles (GNPs) for ultrasensitive detection. The presence or absence of TB analytes in sample solutions is directly linked to the production of various colored solutions by plasmonic nanoparticles in the presence of enzyme labels. The methodology was mostly based on the traditional ELISA procedure, which uses catalase-labeled antibodies to identify illness (61).

6. Conclusion and future prospects

Tuberculosis is a presiding global health challenge and is among the top ten leading infectious causes of death. In order to slow down or control this issue, fast and rapid diagnosis is very important. Conventional TB diagnostic techniques like culture and microscopy are either too laborious or less sensitive. The successful collaboration of nanotechnology with biosensing technology has the potential to boost the rapid detection of TB and for overall management in clinical diagnosis. But at the same time, nanotechnology needs further modification in order to produce something commercially. Therefore, much research is still needed.

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8. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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